

Technical Report

Baseline Surveys of the Coral Reefs in Kilifi and Kwale Counties of Kenya

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Summary

Coral reef benthic and fish abundance surveys were conducted at five sites in Kwale County and three sites in Kilifi County in April, October, and November 2022, led by CORDIO East Africa, for the REEFISH project. The survey provides baseline ecological data for coral reefs areas that are open to fishing for the REEFISH project. The aim of this REEFISH project is to establish community-based management area (CMA) to protect their coral reef systems and improve the resilience of fishing communities.

Surveys were carried out by CORDIO researchers, with assistance from collaborators, following CORDIO's standardized reef survey methods to assess coral reef health. For the benthic assessment, photo quadrats were used to assess the balance of live hard corals to other substrate categories. For fish abundance assessment, standard Underwater Visual Census (UVC) transects were used to estimate the density and size of species from eleven representative families.

In Kwale County reefs were dominated by algae, whereas in Kilifi County reefs were dominated by soft corals, and hard coral cover was higher in Kwale reefs than Kilifi reefs. Hard coral cover ranges from 3.4% at Mapasi to 37.3% at Kilingoni in Kwale County, and from 7.1% at Wembe to 12.8% at Kilifi Plantation in Kilifi County. All sites showed evidence of previous hard coral mortality, likely caused by elevated sea surface temperatures due to global warming. All sites had a lower-than-average fish biomass for the WIO region, which is 900-1,100kg/ha for ocean fringing reefs. However, close to average biomass for the region was recorded in one site in Kwale County. Fish biomass and density were generally higher in the sites in Kwale County than in Kilifi County.

Overall, it appears as though many of the selected target fish families in the sites surveyed are overfished, therefore it is recommended that fisheries management measures such as CMAs is implemented for some sites, particularly for Mapasi and Wembe in Kwale and Kilifi County respectively, to allow local reef and their associated fish stocks to recover. More targeted management to protect herbivorous fish could be considered for areas with high algal cover and low herbivore biomass, such as Mapasi, Mji wa Kale and Jumba Ruins.

Introduction

The coral reefs of Kenya are vulnerable to collapse (Obura *et al.*, 2021). However, if they are protected from local human disturbances through management and policy actions that reduce the sources of degradation, they can recover and be more resilient to future climate change shocks. Some of the accepted strategies to prevent reef decline and encourage natural recovery include protecting reefs from misuse and overuse (such as overfishing and destructive fishing) as well as the reduction of local and global stressors (Obolski *et al.*, 2016). Ecological monitoring of coral reefs is used to understand reef status and trends of benthic groups and fish and can measure the effectiveness of interventions and inform management (Obura, 2014; Obura *et al.*, 2020). Hence, monitoring changes of reef community variables is key to better understanding of the potential benefits of strategy implemented.

This report is an output of the REEFISH project GCP/RAF/520/JPN “*Enhancing Livelihoods, Food Security and Maritime Safety through Increased Resilience of Fishing Communities Dependent on Coral Reef Fisheries in the African Coastal Countries of the Indian Ocean*” project, funded by the Government of Japan and coordinated by FAO in collaboration with the five countries Comoros, Kenya, Madagascar, Mauritius, and Seychelles. The objective of the project is to improve coral reef fisheries production for food security by restoring fragile ecosystems and assisting fishing communities to better manage their coral reef resources. The goal of coral reef monitoring is to collect ecological baseline data to assess the health of coral reefs in order to inform project interventions, provide indicators to evaluate the project's impact, and strengthen regional collaboration in reef conservation and monitoring.

The report provides baseline information from the coral reef monitoring conducted in Kenya as part of the REEFISH project. It focuses on the findings of the reef surveys to provide current baseline conditions for 2022 of the targeted reefs. The report will use information from the fieldwork report submitted to build on the interpretation of the findings and expert knowledge in providing recommendations from the results.

The surveys were conducted between October 16th and November 5th, 2022, and includes data from other sites collected in March and April 2022. The survey was conducted in collaboration with other institutions and members of Beach Management Units (BMU) at their respective locations (see Annex for the list of participants).

Material and Methods

Study sites

The sites in Kwale County were shallow fringing reefs close to shore along the Msambweni shoreline, on Wasini island and inside the Wasini channel. The sites in Kilifi County (Jumba Ruins (Mnazi and Mwariela), Wembe and Kilifi Plantation (Matapani) were deeper, more exposed forereefs (Fig. 1). In Wembe, at the south end of the Vuma cliffs, the forereef starts close to shore. After determining the locations to be surveyed by the project, site selection was determined through discussion with local fishing community leaders, with a focus on their main reef fishing grounds.

Figure 1: Surveyed stations (dives) for sites surveyed in Kwale and Kilifi Counties

Methods

Coral reef health was assessed by surveying benthic and coral communities, and fish populations. Benthic cover provides information on the reef state by indicating the balance between hard corals and other benthic groups such as algae, soft corals etc. Fish biomass is calculated from the fish density and size data collected, which provides a good indication of reef health and levels of overfishing.

Benthic and Coral

The benthic cover was determined using photo quadrats taken randomly 0.7-1 m above the benthic substrate on both sides of a 25m transect. Two stations were sampled, with the first station selected at random from reef areas within the study site and the second station located approximately 500 meters away. Twenty-four photos were selected at random on each station to determine benthic community composition including coral cover (to genus level). The program Coralnet (<https://coralnet.ucsd.edu/>) was used for photo quadrat annotation.

Fish

Eleven families covering 12 trophic groups were selected for surveys. The 11 families provide a broad and representative cross-section of the reef fish community (Table 5) (Samoilys et al. 2018, 2019). Standard underwater visual census (UVC) techniques for coral reef fishes using SCUBA or snorkeling along 50 x 5 m transects (English et al. 1994, Samoilys 1997, Samoilys and Carlos 2000) were employed. Five replicate transects on one or two dives were conducted at each location. Occasionally, only three replicate transects were collected when only one dive was possible. The transects were placed randomly at different depths to span the depth range of the reef.

Fish sizes (Total Length, TL) were estimated in 5cm size classes (11-15cm, 16-20cm, 21-25cm, etc.). Periodic checks were made using a calibrated slate to ensure visual estimates were still accurate. The size of species smaller than 11cm was not estimated, only their numbers were counted, and the median size was taken as 8.0 cm TL. Fish biomass (kg) is then calculated from the density and total length per species using published length-weight conversions.

Twelve trophic groups of fish (Table 5 in Annex) were examined from which two aggregate indicators were calculated. Piscivores-omnivores represent species that have higher fishery value and are targeted in local fisheries and hence provide an indicator of fishing pressure (Samoilys et al. 2019). Herbivores can confer resilience to coral reefs to climate change by controlling algae and therefore represent a coral reef health index (Bellwood et al. 2004, Hughes et al. 2007, Obura et al. 2011; Obura et al. 2017.).

Data Analysis

Benthic and Corals

The percentage cover of each replicate (photo quadrat) was calculated by multiplying the proportion of points per benthos by 4. The site's average coverage for each benthos was then determined by averaging its replicates.

Fish

Biomass was computed using the formula $W = a * L^b$, where W = body weight, L = median of size class, a and b values based on published length–weight relationships (Letourneur 1998, Kulbicki *et al.*, 2005).

Density and biomass were standardized to individuals/hectare and kg/hectare respectively. Density and biomass were computed at three levels; Total density and biomass (mean of all families aggregated), density and biomass at family level, and density and biomass for indicator trophic groups. The indicator trophic were piscivores-omnivores which represent species that are targeted in fishery hence indicator of fishing pressure (Obura *et al.*, 2011).

Results

Kilifi County

Benthic and Corals

Soft coral dominated at Jumba Ruins and Wembe, with covers of $36.3\% \pm 4.9$ (mean \pm standard error) and $48.8\% \pm 5.4$, respectively. Macroalgae and turf algae were dominant at Kilifi Plantation, with mean covers of $43.0\% \pm 4.3$ and $24.7\% \pm 3.2$, respectively. Hard coral cover was $12.8\% \pm 5.1$ at Kilifi plantation, $10.4\% \pm 2.8$ at Jumba Ruins, and $7.1\% \pm 2.7$ at Wembe. Minimal levels of rubble were observed at Jumba Ruins ($0.2\% \pm 0.1$) and Kilifi Plantation ($0.3\% \pm 0.3$), and some presence of dead-standing corals was recorded at Kilifi Plantation with a percentage cover of $0.3\% \pm 0.3$ (figure 2).

Figure 2: Benthic percentage mean cover of the surveyed site at Kilifi County.

The dominant hard coral genus was *Porites* massive, with a mean cover of 7.2% at Kilifi Plantation, 3.6% at Jumba Ruins, and 2.4% at Wembe. *Acropora* was 1.6% in Jumba Ruins and 0.2% in Kilifi Plantation but was not recorded at Wembe.

Table 1: Mean Percentage cover of coral genera at the surveyed sites in Kilifi County

Genus	Sites		
	Jumba Ruins	Wembe	Kilifi Plantation
<i>Acanthastrea</i>	-	0.3	-
<i>Acropora</i>	1.6	-	0.2
<i>Echinopora</i>	0.3	0.8	-
<i>Favia</i>	3.3	0.2	-
<i>Favites</i>	0.2	-	1.0
<i>Galaxea</i>	0.4	0.2	0.2
<i>Montipora</i>	-	0.8	1.7
<i>Platygyra</i>	0.9	1.3	2.0
<i>Pocillopora</i>	-	0.3	-
<i>Porites</i> branching	0.1	-	-
<i>Porites</i> massive	3.6	2.4	7.2
<i>Symphillia</i>	-	0.9	-
Others	-	-	0.7

Fish

Wembe had the highest fish density and biomass at $2,848 \pm 1137.0$ fish/ha (mean \pm standard error) and 497.6 ± 300.3 (kg/ha) (Fig. 3), followed by Jumba ruins and the lowest density and biomass was recorded at Kilifi Plantation.

Figure 3: Fish abundance represented by overall mean density (number of fish/ha) and mean biomass (kg/ha) of the surveyed sites in Kilifi County. The error bars represent standard errors.

Fish assemblages at Wembe were dominated by the family Caesionidae at 1360 ± 1085.2 (fish/ha) and 310.2 ± 567.2 (kg/ha) respectively. Caesionidae was lowest at Jumba Ruins with a mean density of 8 ± 8 (fish/ha) and mean biomass of 0.9 ± 0.9 (kg/ha). The family Acanthuridae were also relatively dominant in the three sites with mean density ranging from 373.3 ± 58.1 (fish/ha) to 768 ± 243.1 (fish/ha) and mean biomass ranging from 71.3 ± 18.2 (kg/ha) to 79.6 ± 32.6 (kg/ha).

Figure 4: Fish abundance family mean density (fish/ha) and mean biomass (kg/ha) of surveyed sites in Kilifi County.

In terms of aggregate indicator trophic groups, herbivores recorded the highest mean density in all three sites compared to piscivores-omnivores, with the highest density (506.7 ± 87.4 fish/ha) found at Kilifi Plantation (Fig. 5). In terms of biomass herbivores only dominated at Kilifi Plantation, where piscivore-omnivore biomass was the lowest (6.6 ± 2.1 kg/ha). The Piscivore-omnivores biomass was the highest and higher than herbivores at Wembe (39.5 ± 17.1 (kg/ha) where piscivores-omnivores density was also higher than the other Kilifi sites (240 ± 68.1 (fish/ha).

Note the highly abundant planktivores (i.e. Caesionidae) at Wembe (Figure 4) are not contained within these aggregate indicators.

Figure 5: Fish abundance (mean density and mean biomass (kg/ha) indicator trophic groups: piscivores-omnivores and herbivores, of the surveyed sites in Kilifi County. The error bars represent the standard errors.

Kwale County

Benthic and corals

Hard coral dominated at Kilingoni (37.3 ± 8.0), Mliani (33.2 ± 3.8), and Ngomani (33.2 ± 4.8), while turf algae dominated at Mapasi (34.9 ± 3.5) and Mji wa Kale (24.4 ± 2.3). Hard coral cover at Mapasi and Mji wa Kale was 3.4 ± 1.2 and 14.5 ± 3.3 , respectively. Kilingoni had the highest cover of macroalgae, followed by Mapasi and Mji wa Kale, which had covers of 29.5 ± 6.1 , 27.8 ± 3.5 and 24.3 ± 4.5 , respectively (figure 6). Other dominant groups include seagrass at Ngomani, with a cover of 22.6 ± 5.1 , and soft coral at Mapasi (20.5 ± 4.3) and Mliani (21.2 ± 2).

Figure 6: Benthic percentage mean cover of the surveyed site at Kwale County. Error bars represent standard error

Montipora was the dominant coral genus at Kilingoni (24.5%) and Mji wa Kale (4.6%), while *Porites* massive was dominant at Ngomani (7.3%), *Galaxea* at Mliani (7.6%), and *Acropora* at Mapasi (1.2%). Ngomani recorded the highest number of different coral genera based on benthic cover data (n=21), followed by Mliani (n=15) and Mji wa Kale (n=13) (table 2).

Table 2: Mean Percentage cover of coral genera at the surveyed sites in Kilifi County

Genus	Sites				
	Kilingoni	Mliani	Ngomani	Mji wa kale	Mapasi
<i>Acanthastrea</i>	-	1	0.1	-	-
<i>Acropora</i>	-	0.4	8.6	2.3	1.2
<i>Astreopora</i>	-	0.3	1.0	0.6	0.1
<i>Cyphastrea</i>	6.0	-	-	-	-
<i>Echinophyllia</i>	-	-	0.2	-	-
<i>Echinopora</i>	4.3	5.9	1.7	0.6	-
<i>Favia</i>	0.2	0.8	-	-	0.2
<i>Favites</i>	0.7	2.2	0.5	0.2	0.3
<i>Fungia</i>	-	0.3	0.1	-	0.3
<i>Galaxea</i>	0.3	7.6	0.3	0.4	0.2
<i>Goniastrea</i>	-	-	0.2	-	-
<i>Goniopora</i>	-	0.8	-	-	-
<i>Hydnophora</i>	-	-	0.1	-	-
<i>Lobophyllia</i>	-	3.5	2.3	-	-
<i>Millepora</i>	-	-	0.1	-	-
<i>Montipora</i>	24.5	3.9	1.8	4.6	-
<i>Pavona</i>	0.2	-	-	0.1	-
<i>Platygyra</i>	1.0	3.6	1.3	-	0.2
<i>Pocillopora</i>	-	-	0.1	0.2	0.1
<i>Porites branching</i>	-	0.3	5.7	2.4	1.0
<i>Porites massive</i>	0.2	2.5	7.3	2.8	-
<i>Seriatopora</i>	-	-	0.7	0.1	-
<i>Stylophora</i>	-	-	0.4	0.1	-
<i>Symphillia</i>	-	0.1	-	-	-
<i>Turbinaria</i>	-	-	0.2	-	-
Others	-	-	0.8	0.2	-

Fish

Overall, the highest fish density and biomass in the Kwale County sites was recorded at Mliani with a mean biomass of 933.3 ± 182.2 (kg/ha) (mean \pm standard error) and a mean density of $3,816 \pm 777.3$ (fish/ha) (Fig. 7). The lowest mean biomass and mean density was recorded at Ngomani with a mean biomass of 176.9 ± 33.6 (kg/ha) and mean density of $1,368 \pm 422.1$ (fish/ha).

Figure 7: Fish abundance represented by overall mean density (number of fish/ha) and mean biomass (kg/ha) of the surveyed sites in Kwale County. The error bars represent standard errors.

The results suggest that the fish assemblages in the majority of the sites was dominated by the Acanthuridae family. However, in Kilingoni and Mliani, the highest biomass was recorded for the family Scarinae and in Ngomani the highest biomass was recorded for Lutjanidae.

Figure 8: Fish abundance family mean density (fish/ha) and mean biomass (kg/ha) of surveyed sites in Kwale County.

In terms of aggregate indicator trophic groups, for both groups the highest biomass for herbivores and piscivores-omnivores was recorded in Mliani at 576.3 ± 118.1 (kg/ha) and 301.7 ± 87.5 (kg/ha) respectively. The same site also recorded the highest density of both herbivores and piscivores-omnivores. The lowest biomass and density of herbivores was recorded in Ngomani with 0.9 ± 0.6 (kg/ha) and 16 ± 9.8 (fish/ha). The lowest biomass and density of piscivores-omnivores was recorded at Mji wa Kale.

Figure 9: Fish abundance (mean density and mean biomass (kg/ha)) indicator trophic groups: piscivores-omnivores and herbivores, of the surveyed sites in Kwale County. The error bars represent the standard errors.

Discussion

The data presented in this report provide a detailed snapshot of the status of coral reefs for the sites surveyed in Kilifi and Kwale Counties in 2022. There is an overall dominance of algae (turf algae and macroalgae) in most of the sites in Kwale County and a dominance of soft coral in all the sites in Kilifi County except at Kilifi Plantation. Almost all the sites had evidence of dead skeletons and old rocks colonized by algae and soft coral, indicative of past mortality of hard corals (Bruckner & Dempsey, 2015). The sites in Kwale County recorded a substantially higher percentage of hard coral cover than the sites in Kilifi County, with some sites in Kwale having over 30% coral cover, while in Kilifi all sites were below 15%. Algal dominance, particularly macro-algae is a sign of poor health of coral reefs and could lead to a permanent phase-shift away from coral dominance. Established macro-algae can stifle coral recruitment and recovery following a disturbance, reinforcing its dominance. The high abundance of soft corals may be an indication of both the high exposure of fore reef sites and past mortality of hard corals, the soft corals preventing a return to a hard coral-dominated state.

Fish biomass and density were generally higher in the sites in Kwale County than in Kilifi County. Acanthuridae were the most abundant in terms of density and biomass except at Mliani where the Scaridae were more abundant. The dominance of Acanthuridae family is typical for reefs characterized by a mixture of habitats (Marshall & Mumby, 2015). Herbivores dominated most reefs, except for Ngomani (Kwale) where Siganidae and Lutjanidae were abundant, and in Jumba Ruins and Wembe where they were equal in biomass to piscivores-omnivores. Mliani (Kwale county) and Wembe (Kilifi) had the highest abundance and biomass of fish overall.

In Kwale County though overall algae (macroalgae and turf algae) cover was dominant, three of the five sites had 30% hard coral cover. This level of hard coral cover is substantially the same as the WIO regional cover that remained after the 1998 bleaching events (Obura et al., 2017), but lower than the Northern Tanzania-Kenya ecoregion average (Obura *et al.*, 2020). Ngomani and Mji wa Kale are found within the Wasini channel and had earlier records of high coral cover (Ochiewo et al., 2017). Mji wa Kale is at the channel's exit at the corner of the Wasini island, and experiences strong wave action, promoting macroalgae (Fabricius & McCorry, 2006). Ngomani, though it had high coral cover had low fish abundance dominated by piscivore-omnivores, indicative of a disturbed reef state (Chabanet et al., 1997). Mapasi had complex topography and was about 8 meters deep, but with the lowest coral cover (<5 %), few target fishery species, and low fish biomass, suggestive of both overfishing of larger targeted fish and poor habitat for these fish taxa (Samoilys et al. 2019). Mliani had high hard coral cover and the highest abundance (density and biomass) of both herbivore and piscivore-omnivore fish. This is likely because the reef is well-developed, with relatively deep and diverse benthic substrates.

Kilifi County sites were dominated by soft coral and algae, together comprising over 80% of the bottom. The Kilifi plantation site was characterized by soft substrates (sand and mud) with coral patches and a low abundance of herbivores, which can support the growth of algae and is detrimental to coral recruits. It was a narrow flat fringing reef (<500m long) at 10m, then with a slope of 30 degrees to about 20m. Wembe reef is close to the cliff edge/shore but drops off steeply to open water and is an area with relatively high current flow and wave action. It had a good hard substrate for hard coral settlement and growth, but soft coral was dominant, likely due to the high wave energy and action. The higher density and biomass of fish in the Wembe site is likely due to its high exposure, including the high number of juvenile groupers. Caesionids (plankton feeders characteristic of reef fronts) dominated the site, and the equivalent piscivore-omnivore biomass to herbivore biomass, imply that fishing is less intense here, likely due to the sites high exposure to waves.

All surveys were conducted on fishing grounds, and fishing was observed at every site. Low coral cover and/or low abundance of fish including fishery target species, are the general findings of this survey and are indicative of reef degradation. A 2019 study on the abundance of reef fish in neighboring Tanzania and Mozambique found average total fish biomass ranged from a low of 370kg/ha (Tanzania) and 460 kg/ha (Mozambique) to ~1,100 kg/ha depending on the reef geomorphology (Samoilys et al. 2019). Taking the total fish biomass estimates reported of 400-800 kg/ha for similar reef types in these two countries only two sites in the current Kenyan survey attain these values: Wembe in Kilifi (~ 500kg/ha) and Mliani in Kwale (~ 900 kg/ha). In Mliani piscivores-omnivores accounted for 300 kg/ha which is at the upper end of the values reported in Samoilys et al. 2019 (70-300kg/ha).

These estimates at Mliani are considerably higher than expected for a relatively shallow reef close to shore that is not formally protected and combined with the relatively high coral cover are encouraging results for the fishing community that live close to the site, at Munje. Community members reported that this site was closed to fishing for some time but subsequently opened, which could explain the high fish biomass.

All other sites in both counties have very low biomass of piscivores-omnivores, suggesting widespread overfishing. The sites in Kilifi recorded particularly low biomass of piscivores-omnivores, ranging from 39.5 kg/ha to 6.6kg/ha, an order of magnitude lower than the mean total biomass for ocean exposed fringing reefs in the region (953kg/ha) (Samoilys et al. 2019). Currently significant damage to Kenya's reefs comes from climate change, and overfishing puts them at risk of collapse (Obura *et al.*, 2021). Coral reefs in Kenya that were bleached in 1998 showed some recovery but were further impacted by more recent bleaching events in 2005, 2010, and 2016 (Gudka et al. 2018). Samoilys *et al.*, 2017 found that Kenya's artisanal coral reef fisheries may be approaching a tipping point and recommended urgent intervention to properly manage reef fish

populations. The results of the current study suggest a substantial further decline in reef fish populations which is of great concern for coastal communities' fishery livelihoods.

Recommendations

- Use the high fish biomass sites in Kilifi (Wembe) and Kwale (Mliani) as flagship sites for desirable reef fish populations and use this status to invest in strict fisheries enforcement and implementation of Locally Managed Marine Areas through the Beach Management Units, to maintain them in this state. Wembe is within the expansion plans of the Kuruwitu LMMA and Mliani was once protected by the community, and this could be revived. Establishing them as flagship LMMA sites could encourage adoption by other BMUs.
- Mapasi's outer reef has underwater caves, overhangs, and crevices that provide natural fish habitat and/or breeding grounds. These areas may be ideal as core sites for protection, to promote recovery of fish populations to increase productivity and stocks.
- Enforce controls on fishing methods that threaten ecologically important reef predators, such as sharks and groupers, which were not found or rarely observed at all sites. The biomass and density of Epinephelidae was highest in Wembe, although it was dominated by juveniles, indicating impactful fishing of the adults.
- Consider managing herbivore populations in areas with high algae cover and low herbivore abundance, such as Mapasi, Mji wa Kale, and Jumba Ruins, to facilitate their ability to graze on macroalgae and create opportunities for coral recruitments. On the other sites, herbivores were seen, but they may need to be protected to increase their population as well.
- Ngomani is outside the proposed LMMA at Kibuyuni and may benefit from fish spillover, though it currently has the lowest fish abundance and biomass in Kwale. Strict controls on fishing gear may enable fish populations to recover to a healthier level.

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Annex

Table 3: Data collectors, affiliations, and their role

#	Researcher/Participant	Organization	Role
1	Swaleh Aboud	CORDIO East Africa	Overall survey leader and Lead on benthic surveys
2	Clare Thouless	CORDIO East Africa	Lead in fish population surveys
3	Melita Samoily	CORDIO East Africa	Lead in fish population surveys at Munje sites (Mliani and Kilingoni)
4	Fatma Hassan	Conservation Education Society	Assisting in fish population surveys on some sites
5	Judy Nduta	REEFolution	Assisting in benthic surveys on some sites
6	Ewout Knoester	REEFolution	Assisting in benthic surveys on some sites
7	Chula Mwagona	CORDIO East Africa	Assisting in benthic surveys on some sites
8	Peter Musila	Arocha Kenya	Assisting with fish Abundance surveys on some sites
9	Kiruwa Ali	Kibuyuni BMU	Community participation and guiding to fishing Reefs
10	Abdalla Usi	Kibuyuni BMU	
11	Haji Shee	Mkwiro BMU	
12	Hamisi Omar	Mkwiro BMU	
13	Umayya Hamza	Mkunguni BMU	
14	Hussein Kiroza	Mkunguni BMU	
15	Collins Katana	Kanamai BMU	
16	Shahame Ali	Kanamai BMU	
17	Ali Garama	Kuruwitu BMU	
18	Peter Kiti	Kuruwitu BMU	
19	Walter Kazungu	Takaungu BMU	
20	Kazungu Karisa	Takaungu BMU	

Table 4: Surveyed sites, dates, and coordinate

County	Location	Site	Station	Surveyed date	Latitude	Longitude
Kwale	Kibuyuni	Ngomani	Ngomani_01	17/10/2022	-4.64668	39.32629
			Ngomani_02		-4.64581	39.3316
	Mkwiro	Mji wa kale	Kijamba cha Mswalie mtume	18/10/2022	-4.65837	39.39407
			Kidomoni		-4.65693	39.3994
	Mkunguni	Mapasi	Mapasi	19/10/2022	-4.47096	39.50707
			Kisondongo		-4.47471	39.50128
	Munje	Kilingoni		30/3/2022	-4.54755	39.46273
		Mliani	Mliani_01	1/4/2022	-4.53723	39.46921
Mliani_02	1/4/2022		-4.53429	39.46857		
Kilifi	Kanamai	Jumbo Ruins	Mnazi	25/10/2022	-3.95232	39.78207
			Mwariela		-3.95686	39.7800
	Kuruwitu	Wembe	Wembe_01	3/11/2022	-3.76209	39.8414
		Wembe	Wembe_02		-3.76662	39.84587
	Takaungu	Kilifi Plantation	Matapani	4/11/2022	-3.66621	39.88277

Table 5: Thirteen families surveyed for abundance and biomass and their 12 trophic group and functional characteristics. All taxa were recorded to species level (not all species are listed here). Those split by body size are species that change diet with size. (Source: Samoily et al 2019).

Functional Group	Notes on feeding habits and selection of species	Group/family	English name or species
Piscivores	top level predators, exert top-down control on lower trophic levels of fish, are vulnerable to overfishing therefore good indicators of the level of fishing on a reef.	Serranidae	All groupers
		Lutjanidae	<i>Aprion viriscens</i> <i>Lutjanus bohar</i>
Omnivores (omnivorous carnivores)	Second-level predators with highly mixed diets including small fish, invertebrates and dead animals. Their abundance a good indicator of fishing pressure	Haemulidae	All sweetlip
		Lethrinidae	All emperor
		Lutjanidae	All snapper except <i>Aprion viriscens</i> & <i>Lutjanus bohar</i>
Corallivores	Obligate and facultative corallivores are a secondary indicator of coral community health.	Chaetodontidae	8 Butterflyfish: <i>C. bennetti</i> , <i>C. lineolatus</i> , <i>C. melannotus</i> , <i>C. meyeri</i> , <i>C. ornatissimus</i> , <i>C. trifascialis</i> , <i>C. trifasciatus</i> , <i>C. zanzibarensis</i>
Invertivores	Feed on coral competitors such as soft corals and sponges, their abundance may be a secondary indicator of stability of these groups and of a phase shift. Also prey on small invertebrates in the benthos.	Pomacanthidae	Angelfish. All species except <i>Centropyge</i> spp. which are grazer-detritivores
		Balistidae	Benthic triggerfish (e.g. <i>Sufflamen</i> spp.)
		Chaetodontidae	Non-corallivore Butterflyfish: all other Chaetodontids except <i>H. zoster</i> and <i>H. diphreutes</i> which are planktivores
Planktivores	Resident on reefs but feed in the water column. Their presence/absence may be related to water column conditions, suitable habitat for shelter or reef features such as passes	Chaetodontidae	<i>Hemitaurichthys zoster</i> , <i>Heniochus</i> spp.
		Balistidae	Triggerfish in the water column eg. <i>Melichthys</i> spp., <i>Odonus niger</i>
		Acanthuridae	<i>A. mata</i> , <i>A. nubilus</i> , <i>A. thompsoni</i> , <i>Paracanthurus hepatus</i> All large <i>Naso</i> (>20cm TL, 16cm for <i>N. hexacanthus</i>), except <i>N. unicornis</i> , <i>N. elegans</i> , <i>N. tuberosus</i> which are Browsers
		Caesionidae	All Fusiliers
Detritivores	Feed on organic matter including diatoms in sediment	Acanthuridae	<i>Ctenochaetus</i> spp.

Functional Group	Notes on feeding habits and selection of species	Group/family	English name or species
	and reef surfaces, high abundances poorly understood, may play an important role in reef repair or be linked to eutrophication		
Grazer-detritivores	Feed on algal turf and sediment to extract detritus, microbes and diatoms; may limit growth of macroalgae	Acanthuridae Pomacanthidae	<i>A. blochii</i> , <i>A. dussumieri</i> , <i>A. leucocheilus</i> , <i>A. nigricauda</i> , <i>A. xanthopterus</i> , <i>A. tennentii</i> <i>Centropyge</i> spp.
Herbivores	Feed on endolithic and epilithic algae, substratum and macro-algae. Exert control on coral-algal dynamics, implicated in determining phase shifts from coral to algal dominance e.g in response to mass coral mortality		
<i>Large excavators</i>	Take few, large, deep bites, and remove calcareous substratum; play a large role in bioerosion	Scarinae	<i>Chlorurus</i> spp. >35cm, e.g. <i>C. strongylocephalus</i> <i>Cetoscarus ocellatus</i> { <i>Bolbometapon muricatum</i> }
<i>Small excavators</i>	Remove algae and substrate; play a smaller role in bioerosion	Scarinae	<i>Chlorurus</i> spp. <36cm
<i>Scrapers</i>	Remove algae, sediment and detritus by closely cropping or scraping the substrate		<i>Scarus</i> spp., <i>Hipposcarus</i> spp.
<i>Browsers</i>	Feed on large macro-algae	Scarinae Acanthuridae Ephippidae Kyphosidae	<i>Calotomus</i> spp. <i>Leptoscarus</i> spp. <i>Naso elegans</i> , <i>N. tuberosus</i> , <i>N. unicornis</i> , other <i>Naso</i> spp. <21cm (<16cm for <i>N. hecacanthus</i>) Bat fish – <i>Platax</i> spp. Rudder fish – <i>Kyphosus</i> spp.
<i>Grazers</i>	Graze epilithic algal turfs, including red algae; likely to limit growth of macroalgae	Acanthuridae Siganidae	<i>Zebrasoma</i> spp. <i>A. nigrofuscus</i> , other <i>Acanthurus</i> spp. e.g, <i>A. lineatus</i> <i>Siganus</i> spp